

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROEMULSION CONTAINING THIOCOLCHICOSIDE FOR TOPICAL DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to formulate and evaluate a Microemulsion system containing thiocolchicoside for effective topical delivery. The pH of the drug was found to be 6.3, which is suitable for topical application. The melting point of thiocolchicoside was determined to be 194 °C, confirming its purity. UV spectroscopy showed a λ max at 276.0 nm, and a standard calibration curve was constructed with a regression coefficient (R^2) of 0.9991, indicating linearity. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of characteristic functional groups without any significant drug-excipient interaction. The prepared microemulsion appeared clear and yellow color. Particle size analysis showed an average droplet size of 41.33 nm with a polydispersity index (PDI) of 30.4, indicating uniform size distribution. Zeta potential was found to be -20.4 mV, suggesting good physical stability. SEM analysis revealed spherical and smooth-surfaced droplets. The entrapment efficiency of the formulation was 45.52 %, demonstrating efficient drug encapsulation. *In-vitro* release studies indicated sustained release of the drug over 8 hours, and kinetic modeling suggested that the release followed the Higuchi model. Stability studies conducted over three months showed no significant changes in physical properties, drug content, or particle size, confirming the formulation's stability. Overall, the micro emulsion system demonstrated promising potential for the topical delivery of thiocolchicoside.

Key words- Micro emulsion, Thiocolchicoside, UV spectroscopy, λ max, regression coefficient, FTIR analysis, Stability studies, *In-vitro* release studies

1. INTRODUCTION

Topical drug delivery systems used for dermal and transdermal diseases. The advantage of the topical route is formulation is directly applied to the skin and increases the permeability of drugs. By using topical drug delivery systems disadvantages of an oral route can be reduced. A targeted drug delivery system increases patient compliance. Inflammation is a local protective response of the body tissue injury (**Ulbrich and Lamprecht 2010**). Topical preparations are used for the localized effects at the site of their application by virtue of drug penetration into the underlying layers of skin or mucous membranes. The main advantage of topical delivery system is that it has ability to deliver drugs more selectively to a specific site

(local action). It provides utilization of drugs with short biological half-life, narrow therapeutic window to increase the duration of action (**Chen *et al.*, 2019**).

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable isotropically clear dispersion of two immiscible liquids, such as oil and water, stabilized by an interfacial film of surfactant molecules, with a size range of 5-200 nm and have very low interfacial tension. Because of their unique solubilization properties, microemulsion have attracted increasing attention as potential drug delivery systems, either as vehicles for topical applications or as bioavailability enhancers for poorly water soluble active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) (**Attwood, D 2014**). The existence of microdomains of different polarity within the same single-phase solution enables both hydrophilic and lipophilic materials to be solubilized. Advantages associated with microemulsions include their thermodynamic stability, optical clarity, ease of preparation, and high diffusion and absorption rates when compared with solvent without the surfactant system (**Gradzielski *et al.*, 2021**).

Thiocolchicoside (TCC) is a semisynthetic sulfur derivative of colchicoside, a natural glycoside present in a plant *Gloriosa superba*. Due to these properties, it is extensively prescribed for the treatment of orthopaedic, traumatic and rheumatologic disorders. TCC is administered orally, intramuscularly or topically for the symptomatic treatment of rheumatologic disorders. It is a muscle relaxant with antiinflammatory and analgesic effects. It has potent convulsant activity and should not administered to individuals prone to seizures (**Bhamburkar *et al.*, 2022**).

Thiocolchicoside binds to GABA-A and strychnine sensitive glycine receptors. Thiocolchicoside acting as a GABA-A receptor antagonist, its myorelaxant effects could be exerted at the supra-spinal level, via complex regulatory mechanisms, although a glycinergic mechanism of action cannot be excluded (**Rathore *et al.*, 2021**). The characteristics of the interaction of Thiocolchicoside with GABA-A receptors are qualitatively and quantitatively shared by its main circulating metabolite, the glucuronidated Derivative. Thiocolchicoside is rapidly absorbed after oral administration, and metabolized into 3 main metabolites. The two main circulating forms were the Thiocolchicoside aglycon and the glucuronidated derivative of Thiocolchicoside, which is active. Thiocolchicoside is well tolerated oral administration for periods of up to 6 months (**Umarkar *et al.*, 2011**).

The main aim of current research is to formulate and evaluate microemulsion containing thiocolchicoside for topical disease

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals

Ethanol, DCM, Methanol, DMSO, n-Octanol, HPMC, Ethyl cellulose, Propylene glycol and Methyl paraben were obtained from Merck, a reputable supplier of analytical reagents. Rankem provided the Methanol, and Sulab provided the Carbopol 934. Loba provided the Triethanolamine. *Sigma-Aldrich* provided the KBr.

2.2 Pre-formulation studies of Drug

Pre-formulation studies were conducted to investigate the physical, chemical, and mechanical properties of the drug substances prior to formulation development.

2.2.1 Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic studies of Thiocolchicoside like general appearance like color, odor, state, etc. were observed (**Agrahari *et al.*, 2021**).

2.2.2 Solubility study

The solubility study of Thiocolchicoside was performed by adding an excess amount of the drug to separate test tubes containing various polar and non-polar solvents. This study helped assess the drug's solubility profile and select suitable solvents for further formulation development (Annepogu *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.3 pH Determination

The pH determination was carried out using a digital pH meter (Aprile *et al.*, 2017).

2.2.4 Melting Point

The melting point of Thiocolchicoside was determined using a digital melting point apparatus (Joshi and Gupta 2013).

2.2.5 Determination of Lambda max and calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

- **Preparation of standard stock solution:**

About 5mg of Thiocolchicoside was weighed and transferred into 5ml volumetric flask (Separately). The volume was made up to 5ml using respective solvent to obtain a solution that has a concentration 1000 µg/ml. 1ml of this stock solution was taken and then diluted up to 10 ml using methanol solvent to obtain a solution that has a concentration 100 µg/ml which is standard stock solution.

- **Lambda max**

From the above stock solution (Thiocolchicoside) 0.5 ml sample was transferred into a 5 ml volumetric flask (separately) and the volume was made up to mark with solvent to prepare a concentration of 10 µg/ml. The sample was scanned by UV-VIS Spectrophotometer in the range of 200- 400 nm for Thiocolchicoside, using methanol solvent as a blank. The wavelength corresponding to the maximum absorbance (max) was found (Kamal *et al.*, 2022).

- **Linearity**

Aliquots of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/ml prepared utilizing 100 µg/ml Thiocolchicoside and working standard solution were accurately transferred into a series of 5 ml calibrated flask and made up to the mark with solvent. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured 276.0 nm for Thiocolchicoside against solvent blank. A calibration curve was created by graphing absorbance versus medication concentration (Bharatbhai, 2013).

A six-point calibration curve was generated for drug concentrations ranging from 5-30 µg/ml. The drug response was determined to be linear in the investigation concentration range and the linear regression equation. (Thiocolchicoside was $y = 0.0363x + 0.0076$ with correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9991$ (Acharjya *et al.*, 2010).

2.2.6 Fourier transmission Infra-Red Spectroscopy

FT-IR spectrum of Thiocolchicoside was recorded over the range of 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ by KBr pellet method using a FT-IR spectrophotometer. The KBr disc was prepared using 1 mg of each Thiocolchicoside in 100 mg of spectroscopic grade KBr which has been dried using IR lamp. Both KBr and drug was mixed and subjected to hydraulic pressure to form disc. This disc was placed in FT-IR chamber. Infrared spectrum was recorded in the 4000 - 400 cm⁻¹ region.

2.3 Formulation of micro emulsion

The solubility of drug in various oils (oleic acid, Capryol 90, olive oil), surfactants (Cremophor RH 40, Tween 80), and cosurfactants (polyethylene glycol 400) was tested by first adding an excess amount of drugs in 2 mL of selected excipients into 5 mL stopper vials, followed by vortex mixing. Oil, surfactant, and co-surfactant were chosen based on their medication solubility. The micro-emulsion of the appropriate composition, as indicated in table 2, was created utilizing four components: olive oil as the oil phase, tween 80 as a surfactant, propylene glycol as a co-surfactant, and distilled water as the aqueous phase. Batches were designed for different surfactant–co-surfactant ratios. A ratio of surfactant and co-surfactant e,S/CoS chosen and corresponding mixture was made. The mixture was mixed with oil. Each mixture was mixed thoroughly using magnetic stirrer until homogenous dispersion/solution was obtained. These formulations used double-distilled water to prevent the inclusion of surface active contaminants (Sabale and Vora 2012).

Table 1: Composition of micro emulsion formulation

Ingredients	FORMULATION CODE				
	Micro emulsion (F1)	Micro emulsion (F2)	Micro emulsion (F3)	Micro emulsion (F4)	Micro emulsion (F5)
Drug (%)	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
Propylene Glycol (ml)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
Tween 80 (ml)	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Olive oil (ml)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Stirring Time (min.)	30	30	30	30	30
Distilled water	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

2.4 Evaluation parameter of drug loaded micro emulsion

2.4.1 Physical appearance

The prepared micro emulsion formulation was evaluated for appearance, Color, Odor, and homogeneity by visual observation (Abbas *et al.*, 2019).

2.4.2 Particle size

The particle size is one of the most important parameter for the characterization of micro emulsion. The size of micro emulsion was measured using Malvern Zeta sizer (Malvern Instruments) (Singh and Vingkar 2008).

2.4.3 Zeta potential

In the present work, the micro emulsion was diluted 10 times with distilled water and analyzed by Zetasizer Malvern instruments. All samples were sonicated for 5-15 minutes before zeta potential measurements (Fatehi *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.4 Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM)

The morphological properties of the drug-loaded micro emulsion were obtained using an electron beam from a scanning electron microscope. A thin layer (2-20 nm) of metal(s) such as gold, palladium, or platinum was applied using a sputter coater under vacuum conditions. From the interaction between the electron beam and the specimen's atoms, only the electrons scattered at 90° were selected and further processed based on Rutherford and Kramer's Law for acquiring the images of surface topography (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.5 Quantitative analysis (Entrapment Efficiency)

Entrapment efficiency was determined by indirect estimation. Drug -loaded micro emulsion were centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 30 min using REMI Ultra Centrifuge. The peak area was determined and amount of free drug is determined by extrapolating the calibration curve. And drug entrapment calculated by using below equation (Balla and Goli 2020).

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency \%} = \frac{\text{Total drug conc.} - \text{Supernatant drug conc.}}{\text{total drug conc.}} \times 100$$

2.4.6 In-vitro drug release study

The *in-vitro* drug release study of Thiocolchicoside loaded micro emulsion formulation was studied by dialysis bag diffusion method. Thiocolchicoside loaded micro emulsion was dispersed into dialysis bag and the dialysis bag was then kept in a beaker containing 100 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The beaker was placed over a magnetic stirrer and the temperature of the assembly was maintained at 37 ± 2 °C throughout the experiment. During the experiment rpm was maintained at 100 rpm. Samples (2 ml) were removed at predetermined intervals and replaced with equal volumes of new pH 7.4 phosphate buffers. To analyses the *in vitro* drug release data, multiple kinetic models were utilized to describe the release kinetics.

To assess the *in vitro* release data, many kinetic models were used to describe the release kinetics. The zero order rate equation represents settings in which the drug release rate is independent of concentration. The first order equation depicts the release from a system whose release rate is concentration dependent. Higuchi defined drug release from an insoluble matrix as a time-dependent square root process based on Fickian diffusion. The results of the *in vitro* release profiles obtained for all formulations were shown using data treatment modalities (Solomon *et al.*, 2017).

2.5 Stability study

The micro emulsion formulation was packed and were placed in the stability test chamber and subjected to stability studies at accelerated testing ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $60 \pm 5\%$ RH) and ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $70 \pm 5\%$ RH) for 3 months. The formulations were checked for evaluation particle size and Entrapment efficiency studies at the interval of 30, 45, 60, 90 days (3 month) months. The formulation was tested for stability under accelerated storage condition for 3 months in accordance to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines (González-González *et al.*, 2022).

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Pre-formulation study

3.1.1 Organoleptic properties

Table 2: Organoleptic properties of Thiocolchicoside

Drug	Organoleptic properties	Observation
Thiocolchicoside	Colour	Light to dark yellow
	Odour	Odour less
	Appearance	Solid powder
	State	Solid

3.1.2 Solubility study

Table 3: Solubility study of Thiocolchicoside

Drug	Solvents	Observation/Inference
Thiocolchicoside	Water	Soluble
	Ethanol	Soluble
	Methanol	Freely soluble
	Chloroform	Slightly soluble
	DMSO	Freely soluble

3.1.3 Determination of pH, melting point and Lambda max of Thiocolchicoside

Table 4: pH, melting point and Lambda max of Thiocolchicoside

Drugs	Observed (pH)	Observed (Melting Point)	Reference (Melting Point)	UV absorption maxima (Lambda max)
Thiocolchicoside	6.3	194°C	190 -198 °C	276.0 nm

3.1.5 Calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

Graph 1: Calibration curve of Thiocolchicoside

3.1.6 Functional group identified by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) study

1. FTIR of Thiocolchicoside

Graph 2: FTIR of Thiocolchicoside

Table 6:- Interpretation of IR spectrum of Thiocolchicoside

Peak obtained	Reference peak	Functional group	Name of functional group
3396.93	3400-3300	N-H stretching	Aliphatic primary amine
2921.86	3000-2840	C-H stretching	Alkane
1560.80	1650-1580	N-H bending	Amine
1154.74	1165-1150	S=O stretching	Sulfonic acid
1070.71	1085-1050	C-O stretching	Primary alcohol

3.2 Characterization of optimized formulation

3.2.1 Particle size determination

Graph 3: Particle size (F1)

Graph 4: Particle size (F2)

Graph 5: Particle size (F3)

Table 7: Result of Particle size of all formulations

Formulations	Particle size (nm)	PI Value
Micro emulsion (F1)	54.82 nm	29.5 %
Micro emulsion (F2)	55.35 nm	30.3 %
Micro emulsion (F3)	72.04 nm	24.3 %
Micro emulsion (F4)	41.33 nm	30.4 %
Micro emulsion (F5)	47.43 nm	26.6 %

Graph 8:- Particle size and PI value of all formulations

3.2.2 Zeta potential determination

Table 8: Result of Zeta potential of all formulations

Formulation	Zeta potential
Micro emulsion (F1)	-13.9 mV
Micro emulsion (F2)	-19.8 mV
Micro emulsion (F3)	-11.7 mV
Micro emulsion (F4)	-20.4 mV
Micro emulsion (F5)	-10.1 mV

Graph 14:- Zeta potential graphical representations

3.2.3 Entrapment efficacy

Table 9: Entrapment efficacy

Formulations (F1-F5)	Entrapment efficacy (%)
Micro emulsion (F1)	91.33
Micro emulsion (F2)	82.37
Micro emulsion (F3)	89.39
Micro emulsion (F4)	95.52
Micro emulsion (F5)	83.29

Graph 15:- entrapment efficacy graphical representation

3.2.4 Scanning electron microscopy characterization of F4 formulation

Figure 1: SEM

Table: 10 Release studies of all formulations

Time (Hr)	cumulative % drug released F1	cumulative % drug released F2	cumulative % drug released F3	cumulative % drug released F4	cumulative % drug released F5
0	0	0	0	0	0
2	20.45	29.81	13.07	23.11	28.32
3	36.86	40.76	21.66	36.1	40.10
4	46.91	66.86	32.04	43.13	46.78
5	67.86	74.11	47.33	57.59	60.88
6	75.44	86.08	62.78	66.83	72.22
7	89.23	91.23	69.22	77.17	79.25
8	95.46	93.46	74.25	82.41	84.26
9	95.88	93.91	77.86	97.14	91.78

Graph 16:- Release studies of all formulations

3.3.5 *In-vitro* drug release

Table 11: Release kinetics study of optimized micro-emulsion formulation

Time (Hr)	cumulative % drug released	% drug remaining	Square root time	log Cumu % drug remaining	log time	log Cumu % drug released
0	0	100	0.000	2.000	0.000	0.000
2	23.11	76.89	1.414	1.886	0.301	1.364
3	36.1	63.9	1.732	1.806	0.477	1.558
4	43.13	56.87	2.000	1.755	0.602	1.635
5	57.59	42.41	2.236	1.627	0.699	1.760
6	66.83	33.17	2.449	1.521	0.778	1.825
7	77.17	22.83	2.646	1.359	0.845	1.887
8	82.41	17.59	2.828	1.245	0.903	1.916
9	97.14	2.86	3.000	0.456	0.954	1.987

Table 12: Regression coefficient (R2 Value)

Models	R2 Value
Zero order kinetics	$y = 10.539x + 2.196$, $R^2 = 0.9949$
First order kinetic	$y = 0.1537x + 2.2859$, $R^2 = 0.8126$
Higuchi model kinetics	$y = 32.404x - 12.189$, $R^2 = 0.9237$
Korsmeyer peppas	$y = 1.7981x + 0.4372$, $R^2 = 0.8403$

3.4 Stability study

Table 13: Stability Study of optimized formulation (Micro emulsion)

Time (Days)	25°C±2 °C and 60 ± 5% RH		40°C±2 °C and 70 ±5% RH	
	Particle size	Entrapment efficacy (%)	Particle size	Entrapment efficacy (%)
0	41.33 nm	95.52%	41.33 nm	95.52%
30	42.23 nm	96.35%	41.88 nm	95.89%
45	40.87 nm	96.79%	42.13 nm	96.23%
60	43.12 nm	94.84%	40.53 nm	95.86 %
90	42.97 nm	95.74%	41.90 nm	96.14%

4. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the Microemulsion containing thiocolchicoside was effectively formulated and exhibited desirable physicochemical characteristics for topical drug delivery. The formulation provided enhanced solubility, high entrapment efficiency, and controlled drug release, which are critical for achieving localized therapeutic effects while minimizing systemic exposure. The kinetic modeling suggested diffusion-controlled release, which is advantageous for prolonged action. Based on the experimental findings, the developed microemulsion offers a promising platform for the topical delivery of thiocolchicoside in the treatment of localized musculoskeletal conditions such as muscle spasms and inflammation. Future studies involving in-vivo assessments and clinical trials could further establish its potential for commercial and therapeutic use.

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